

Conference Abstract

Low (COI) differentiation between the *Carabus hungaricus* populations in the Carpathian basin

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Abstract

The main goal of our study was to analyse the differences between *Carabus hungaricus* populations in different regions in the Carpathian basin, and to clear the taxonomic rank of the three subspecies living in the area. We performed analyses of mitochondrial genes (COI) to analyse regional isolation besides taxonomic questions. Extensive sampling was performed spatially, focusing also on the different habitat types hosting *C. hungaricus* populations. Low differences were found based on mitochondrial genes (COI) between populations living in the Carpathian basin. Neither spatial nor habitat based differences were significant. Some difference were found in the COI sequences from Deliblato sands (Serbia), while significant difference in the COI sequences was found when analysing specimen from the Crimea. The question arises: was there a refugia for *Carabus hungaricus* within the Carpathian basin in the Ice Ages? To answer this question further research is needed.

Keywords

Carabus hungaricus, COI, Carpathian basin

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